

Socioeconomic Inequality in Health Care Use Among Elderly Russians

Olga A. Kislitsyna¹, Tatiana V. Chubarova^{2,1}

¹ *Institute of Economics of the Russian Academy of Sciences (the RAS), Moscow, 117218, Russia*

² *Shenzhen MSU-BIT University, Shenzhen, 518172, P.R. China*

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Abstract

Data from international studies indicate the existence of socio-economic inequalities in the use of health services by the population, which vary depending on the country, type of service and membership in a particular socio-demographic group. However, the problem of socio-economic differences in healthcare in Russia, especially for older people, has not received due attention. At the same time, population ageing is a serious problem in many countries, including Russia. The increase in the proportion of elderly people leads to an increase in those in need of medical care, so ensuring the availability of medical services for this population group is becoming increasingly important. The aim of the study is to assess socioeconomic inequalities in the use of health services among older Russians. The information base of the study is the data of the Comprehensive Survey of Living Standards of the Population (CSLS), conducted in 2022, on the basis of which multivariate logistic regression models were built. The study found socioeconomic inequalities in the use of health care by older patients. Compared with individuals in the highest quintile of household per capita income, individuals in lower quintiles have lower odds of using outpatient and inpatient services. Older adults with lower levels of education are less likely to use outpatient and inpatient care, and employed older adults are less likely to use all types of services compared to those who are not employed. The analysis concluded that it is important to create a more equitable healthcare system, where every person, regardless of age and socioeconomic status, can receive the medical care they need.

Keywords

health care utilization; socioeconomic inequality; older people; outpatient care; inpatient services; emergency care; Comprehensive Living Standards Survey

JEL codes: I12, I14, C21

Introduction

Socioeconomic inequalities in access to and use of health services are a major public health problem worldwide. It is observed in many countries, regardless of their level of economic development and organization of the healthcare system (Devaux 2015; Moscelli et al. 2018; Mulyanto et al. 2019; Xu et al. 2019; Vahedi et al. 2020; Gordon et al. 2020).

Because low socioeconomic status is associated with poor health (Mackenbach 2006), one might expect that people with lower social status use more health care resources than people at the other end of the socioeconomic gradient (van Kippersluis et al. 2010). However, research shows that socioeconomic inequality favours both the poor and the rich (Cai et al. 2024). Inequality in favour of the rich means that the rich use more health care. Pro-poor inequality, on the other hand, means that more health services are used by the poor. Inequalities in favour of rich and poor in the use of health services have been documented for both different types of services and different population groups.

The ageing population leads to an increase in the number of people in need of health care (WHO 2015), so providing health services to this demographic group is important. International research data show that there are socioeconomic inequalities in the use of health services by older citizens, the extent of which varies depending on the country and the type of service used (Gao et al. 2022; Almeida et al. 2017). It appears that the problem of socio-economic inequality in access to healthcare in Russia, including in terms of individual socio-demographic groups of the population, has not received due attention. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to assess socio-economic inequality in the use of health services by elderly Russians. The obtained results will expand the existing knowledge base on the influence of socio-economic risk factors on the use of health care by the elderly population and, accordingly, will contribute to the justification of the need to improve the organization of the health care system in order to ensure equality of patients, regardless of their socio-economic status.

Socioeconomic Inequality in Health Care: Research Methodology

The problem of inequality in health care has become quite acute in recent times. Researchers pay special attention to its socio-economic aspect, that is, inequality caused not by medical (biological or genetic), but by socio-economic factors. This approach is based on the idea of health determinants, which has recently been developed in the works of Russian researchers, both theoretically and empirically (Kartseva and Kuznetsova 2023; Kislitsyna 2020, 2023; Chubarova 2024).

Research devoted to various aspects of socio-economic inequality can be divided into two large groups (Lyadova 2020): the study of inequalities in health status and in the position of citizens in the healthcare system. This article examines the second direction, where the main subject is the availability of health services, or, more precisely, medical services in the context of the socio-economic status of citizens in modern society. It has been observed that such inequality is present in countries with different levels of socio-economic development.

Particular attention to this issue at both the international and national levels is associated with the following approaches: the idea of universal access, when the need to organize healthcare in such a way as to provide medicine for everyone is recognized at the political

level; an understanding of the injustice of socio-economic inequality, which is predominantly perceived negatively by society, including in Russia (Kislitsyna 2018).

From a methodological point of view, clarifications are needed due to the complexity of measuring access to health care. Access is understood as the ability of a citizen to receive the necessary set of medical services in a timely manner in accordance with the need to achieve the best health outcomes. Currently, the task of healthcare systems worldwide is recognized as ensuring universal access. This means that all citizens should receive a full range of necessary services, from prevention to rehabilitation, if necessary. However, the situation is complicated by the fact that access is a multidimensional phenomenon, including infrastructural, financial and cultural aspects. Therefore, difficulties arise in its specific measurement, primarily for management purposes and evaluation of government programmes.

It seems that, in a broad sense, availability should be viewed as an umbrella term that combines three more specific indicators: coverage (what citizens are entitled to receive in the health care system in accordance with the law); access (implies that the system is organized in such a way that a citizen has the opportunity to receive medical care if the need arises); utilization (the citizen actually received medical care). Therefore, for further analysis, we selected the use of medical services, which, in our opinion, reflects the actual use of medical care by those in need.

The focus of the research is on elderly citizens. The classification of the elderly as a separate socio-demographic group is justified due to their special needs for medical care. Older adults are more likely to have chronic diseases, functional impairments, and cognitive decline, requiring specialized health services and support (Khan et al. 2024). In addition, they often face unique challenges related to employment, retirement, and financial security that can impact their access to healthcare and overall well-being (Thornton and Bowers 2024). Currently, population ageing is becoming a serious socio-demographic and medical problem in many countries, including Russia. The number of citizens aged 60 and over in the Russian Federation as of January 1, 2024 was approximately 35 million people (24% of the total population) and, according to estimates (UN 2024), will increase to 43 million people (32%) in 2050.

Data and methods

The information basis of the study is data from the Comprehensive Survey of Living Standards of the Population, conducted in 2022¹, during which 123.201 people were interviewed, from which respondents aged 60 years and older (35.269 people in total) were selected for further analysis.

Dependent variables

The use of outpatient, inpatient and emergency services are dependent variables. Respondents were asked the following questions: “Have you sought outpatient care at a medical facility this year?”; “Have you been hospitalized (were you inpatient) this year?”; “Have you had to call an ambulance this year?” Three variables were created, coded as 1 if respondents answered affirmatively to the question and 0 otherwise.

1 Federal State Statistics Service. Comprehensive monitoring of living conditions of the population. 2022. https://rosstat.gov.ru/free_doc/new_site/GKS_KOUZH_2022/index.html

Independent variables

The factors determining the use of health services are grouped into three categories in accordance with Andersen's behavioural model (Andersen 1995), namely:

(i) factors that facilitate or hinder the use of health services:

- socio-economic status, including the level of per capita monetary income (Q1 – the poorest group, with incomes from 0 to 13.750 rubles / Q2 (13.750-17.500 rubles) / Q3 (17.500-22.500 rubles) / Q4 (22.500-27.500 rubles) / Q5 – the richest group with incomes above 27.500 rubles);
- level of education (low/medium/high);
- employment status (working/not working);
- type of settlement (metropolis (1 million residents or more) / large city (250 thousand – 1 million) / medium or small city (less than 50 thousand – 250 thousand) / village);

(ii) predisposing factors that create conditions for seeking medical help:

- gender (male/female);
- age (60-69, 70-79, 80 years and older);
- marital status (married (registered or unregistered) or single (never married/widowed/divorced));

(iii) factors of need that reflect the necessity of medical care:

- health status, assessed using a self-assessment of health status on a five-point scale (1 – very poor, 5 – very good health), dichotomized as good (scores 5, 4, 3) and poor (scores 1, 2) health;
- Health risk factors included smoking (non-smokers/ex-smokers/smokers) and alcohol consumption (yes/no).

Statistical analysis was performed using multivariate logistic regression models of the IBM SPSS Statistics version 26 package.

Results

During the year under review, 16.3% of elderly respondents made outpatient visits, 11.2% were hospitalized, and 19.4% called an ambulance.

Table 1 presents the results of multivariate logistic regression predicting factors associated with older adults' use of different types of health care.

All three indicators of the social status of elderly respondents are associated with the use of medical services (Table 1). Compared with those with high incomes, those in the low and middle income group are less likely to use outpatient (e.g. for the lowest income group Q1 OR = 0.834 CI:0.764-0.911) and inpatient (for Q1 OR = 0.778 CI:0.678-0.892) services. Compared with the highly educated, those with a low level of education are less likely to use outpatient (OR = 0.760 CI:0.711-0.813) and inpatient (OR = 0.866 CI:0.778-0.964) services. Unemployment increases the likelihood of using outpatient (OR = 1.196 CI:1.111-1.287), inpatient (OR=1.322 CI:1.158-1.509) services and emergency care (OR = 1.481 CI:1.316-1.666).

The analysis showed that poor health significantly increases the likelihood of using outpatient (OR = 2.268 CI:2.137-2.407), inpatient (OR = 2.783 CI:2.580-3.001) services and emergency care (OR = 3.133 CI:2.944-3.333) and does not affect the relationship between socioeconomic status and the use of all types of health services.

Table 1. Multivariate logistic regression models for use of different types of health care (odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI))

	Outpatient services		Inpatient services		Emergency services	
	OR	CI	OR	CI	OR	CI
Gender (Male vs Female)	0.632***	(0.595-0.671)	1.097	(0.997-1.207)	0.776***	(0.715-0.842)
Age						
70-79 vs 60-69	1.329***	(1.262-1.400)	1.203***	(1.111-1.303)	1.449***	(1.356-1.549)
80 and older vs 60-69	1.053	(0.976-1.139)	1.019	(0.910-1.141)	2.122***	(1.943-2.318)
Marital Status (Single vs Married)	1.026	(0.978-1.076)	1.022	(0.947-1.103)	1.062	(0.997-1.131)
Health (Bad vs Good)	2.268***	(2.137-2.407)	2.783***	(2.580-3.001)	3.133***	(2.944-3.333)
Education						
Low vs High	0.760***	(0.711-0.813)	0.866**	(0.778-0.964)	1.036*	(1.000-1.132)
Average vs High	1.076*	(1.012-1.143)	1.077	(0.978-1.186)	1.108**	(1.021-1.202)
Income						
Q1 vs Q5	0.834***	(0.764-0.911)	0.778***	(0.678-0.892)	0.957	(0.851-1.075)
Q2 vs Q5	0.876***	(0.808-0.950)	0.782***	(0.690-0.887)	0.915	(0.822-1.019)
Q3 vs Q5	0.971	(0.894-1.053)	0.857**	(0.756-0.972)	0.961	(0.864-1.070)
Q4 vs Q5	1.045	(0.953-1.146)	0.904	(0.784-1.042)	0.964	(0.854-1.087)
Employment (Not Working vs Working)	1.196***	(1.111-1.287)	1.322***	(1.158-1.509)	1.481***	(1.316-1.666)
Type of settlement						
Big City vs Metropolis	0.871**	(0.795-0.955)	0.850*	(0.734-0.983)	1.307***	(1.163-1.470)
Medium and small city vs. Metropolis	0.756***	(0.701-0.815)	1.091	(0.971-1.225)	1.295***	(1.173-1.429)
Village vs. Metropolis	0.666***	(0.615-0.721)	1.083	(0.958-1.224)	1.004	(0.904-1.115)
Smoking						
Ex-smokers vs. Non-smokers	1.225***	(1.133-1.325)	1.331***	(1.187-1.492)	1.360***	(1.231-1.503)
Smokers vs. Non-smokers	0.810***	(0.751-0.874)	0.919	(0.809-1.043)	0.958	(0.859-1.069)
Alcohol consumption (Yes vs No)	1.079**	(1.028-1.133)	0.741***	(0.684-0.802)	0.747***	(0.700-0.798)

Source: Authors' calculations. Note: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001.

Other factors associated with health service use include gender, age, settlement type, smoking and alcohol consumption. Thus, compared with women, men are less likely to use outpatient services (OR = 0.632 CI:0.595-0.671) and call an ambulance (OR = 0.776 CI:0.715-0.842). Compared with the younger age group of 60-69 years, the elderly aged 70-79 years more often use outpatient, inpatient services and emergency care (respectively, OR = 1.329 CI:1.262-1.400, OR = 1.203 CI:1.111-1.303, OR = 1.449 CI:1.356-1.549), and those aged 80 years and older call an ambulance (OR = 2.122 CI:1.943-2.318).

Compared with residents of metropolises, those living in villages (OR = 0.666 CI:0.615-0.721) and cities with fewer residents (for large cities OR = 0.871 CI:0.795-0.955, for medium and small cities OR = 0.756 CI:0.701-0.815) are less likely to use outpatient care. Residents of large cities are less likely to use hospital services (OR = 0.850 CI:0.734-0.983). While compared to residents of metropolises, those living in cities are more likely to call an ambulance (for large cities OR=1.307 CI:1.163-1.470, for medium and small cities OR = 1.295 CI:1.173-1.429).

Compared with non-smokers, smokers are less likely to seek outpatient care (OR = 0.810 CI:0.751-0.874), while former smokers, on the contrary, are more likely to use outpatient clinics (OR = 1.225 CI:1.133-1.325), inpatient services (OR = 1.332 CI:1.187-1.492) and call an ambulance (OR = 1.360 CI:1.231-1.503). Alcohol consumers are more likely to use outpatient services (OR = 1.079 CI:1.028-1.133), but less likely to use inpatient services (OR = 0.741 CI:0.684-0.802) and emergency care (OR = 0.747 CI: 0.700-0.798).

Discussion

The study found that older respondents were more likely to call an ambulance than to visit an outpatient clinic, which is consistent with the findings of other authors (Platts-Mills et al. 2010). One of the main reasons may be that older adults may face difficulties when visiting outpatient facilities, such as long queues, the need to wait, as well as financial aspects – the need to pay for services or transportation (Coster et al. 2017). In addition, older adults may have physical limitations that make it difficult for them to travel to the clinic (Horibata and Takemura 2015). In some cases, they may not realize how serious their situation is and prefer to call an ambulance to get help as quickly as possible (Mills et al. 2023). It may also be due to a lack of awareness of available medical services, leading to the choice of a more emergency option for seeking help.

The study revealed socioeconomic inequalities in the use of medical care by elderly patients in Russia. It has been established that older people with low incomes are less likely to use outpatient and inpatient services compared to their wealthier peers. No effect of income was found with respect to the use of ambulance services.

Low-income older adults may be less likely to seek outpatient medical care and be hospitalized for several reasons (Chi et al. 2024). First, low incomes can limit access to health services due to high costs of treatment, transportation, and medications. Older adults may avoid seeking help if they fear they will not be able to cover costs. Second, low-income older adults may experience social isolation, which may reduce their motivation to seek health care (Zhou et al. 2023). Third, older adults, especially those from low-income groups, may not have sufficient information about available health services or their rights to receive health care (MacLeod et al. 2017). Moreover, older adults with higher incomes pay more attention to their health and undergo regular medical examinations compared to the rest of the population (Langa et al. 2009).

Education level and employment are also associated with health care use. Older adults with lower levels of education are less likely to seek outpatient and inpatient care than their highly educated peers. One possible mechanism for the link between education and health care utilization may be health literacy (van der Heide et al. 2013). Older adults, particularly those with lower levels of education, often have low levels of health literacy, which reduces access to health information and the ability to make informed choices, subsequently exacerbating socioeconomic inequalities in health (Kickbusch et al. 2013).

Working older adults are less likely to use outpatient, inpatient services and call emergency services compared to non-working adults, which is consistent with the findings of studies for the general population (Kisilitsyna 2023). The obtained result can be explained by the fact that, on the one hand, the health of working elderly citizens is generally better than that of non-working ones; on the other hand, the need to continue working for the elderly may be associated with financial difficulties (Gerber and Radl 2014), which limits access to necessary medical services due to lack of funds. Lack of time for workers to seek medical care may also play an important role.

Furthermore, poor health is associated with greater health care use but does not significantly moderate the association between socioeconomic status and health care use.

Similar results were obtained by other researchers. Recent country-specific reviews have found that higher income and higher education levels are associated with greater use of health care (Gao et al. 2022; Almeida et al. 2017). And some studies have found that unemployed older adults were more likely to use health care (Almeida et al. 2017; Zhang et al. 2023). Inequality in the use of inpatient services is slightly higher than that of outpatient services, which confirms the findings of other researchers (Zhang et al. 2023), who explain this by the fact that inpatients face more serious illnesses and hospitalization costs are often higher than outpatient costs (Wang et al. 2012). The studies conducted by foreign authors do not reveal a connection between the socio-economic characteristics of citizens and the use of emergency services (Almeida et al. 2017).

It should be noted that in some countries, results have been found to favour the poor (Gao et al. 2022): for example, in Cuba (Albanese et al. 2011), Brazil (Macinko et al. 2018), China (Albanese et al. 2011), Thailand (Somkotra 2013), older people with lower income and education levels are more likely to use primary health care services. The researchers explain this by the fact that, as shown by the Universal Health Coverage (UHC) Index, Cuba, Brazil, China and Thailand have achieved greater success compared to most countries included in the review: the coverage index in these countries was 78, 77, 76 and 75 points out of 100, respectively. For comparison, for Russia it is 63 points (Gao et al. 2022).

The study showed that, compared with residents of metropolises, those living in cities and villages were less likely to use outpatient services, and residents of large cities were less likely to use inpatient medical care, which is partially consistent with other studies (Zhang et al. 2023; Zhu et al. 2017; Joe et al. 2015; Banerjee 2021). It should be noted that living in a metropolis reduces the likelihood of using an ambulance compared to other types of settlements, which can be explained by several reasons. In metropolises, as a rule, there are more medical organizations, so the availability of outpatient services is higher, while in smaller towns and villages there may be a lack of such institutions (Chernyshev et al. 2022; Belova 2017), which reduces the use of outpatient care. Residents of metropolitan areas may have higher incomes, which allows them to use outpatient and inpatient services more often. At the same time, in small towns and villages, citizens may face financial barriers when seeking medical care. In cities, especially smaller ones, residents may

be more likely to seek emergency care due to a lack of alternative options for receiving help in urgent situations.

Particular attention should be paid to paid medical services. In Russia, their growth has been observed recently, which is reflected, among other things, in the increase in private spending by citizens on medical services. It is likely that the need to pay limits their use by low-income older people. However, the existence of a public health care system where free services are available should be seen as an argument in favour of accessibility.

The results obtained regarding other factors associated with the use of health care by the elderly confirm the findings of previous studies (Li et al. 2024; Wang et al. 2012; Gong et al. 2016): men are less likely to use health care, which may be explained by gender differences (higher morbidity in women; gender differences in perception and attitudes towards health); the use of health services increases with age, which is obviously due to the fact that the aging of the population is accompanied by an increase in non-communicable diseases; the use of health care in general is lower for smokers and alcoholics than for non-smokers and non-drinkers, which can be explained by the fact that regular users of health services are more aware of the risks associated with behaviour that affects health (Vikum et al. 2012).

However, the study conducted has certain limitations. Firstly, the nature of the data does not allow for the identification of cause-and-effect relationships. Secondly, the dependent variables used are based on respondents' subjective judgments, which may not accurately reflect actual use of health care. Third, due to lack of data, the study may miss other possible factors influencing health care use. As an area for future research, it seems appropriate to analyze regional differences in access to health services for the elderly.

Conclusions

The results of the study revealed the existence of socio-economic inequalities in the use of outpatient and inpatient services by elderly Russians.

From a political and managerial perspective, the problem is that socioeconomic inequalities are often not overtly evident, but nevertheless have an impact on both the health of citizens and the performance of the health care system. Therefore, in our opinion, taking this fact into account is important for organizing the system of providing medical care to the population and ensuring its accessibility.

Of course, it is necessary to create a more equitable healthcare system, where every person, regardless of socio-economic status, can receive the necessary medical care. However, this is a complex and challenging task, as the causes of inequality largely lie outside the actual provision of medical care. The Russian healthcare system is an interesting example in this regard, since despite the almost universal coverage of the state system, studies have recorded socio-economic inequalities in the availability and use of medical services between different groups of the population.

Under these conditions, it seems important:

- 1) to recognize the existence of socio-economic inequality in the use of health services among elderly Russians at the political level as a problem and task for the health care system in a broad sense. Therefore, in order to achieve fairness in access to health services, it is necessary, in addition to developing the health care system itself, to also implement programs to combat poverty and ensure adequate social protection for the elderly. In this context, it is

possible, for example, to use mobile clinics to organize services for the rural population, social taxis to organize free transportation for elderly patients, and subsidies for medicines for low-income citizens;

2) to develop indicators that will reflect the level of such inequality in order to use them for making and evaluating management decisions. The study found that the use of health services is a more adequate measure of the real picture.

In conclusion, we would like to note that mitigating inequality in access to medical care for various population groups and studying the social, cultural, economic and geographical factors that influence it should become the basis of policies aimed at ensuring the availability of medical services in Russia.

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Information about the authors

- Olga Anatolyevna Kislitsyna – Doctor of Economics, Chief Research Fellow, Institute of Economics of the Russian Academy of Sciences (the RAS). Moscow, 117218, Russia. E-mail: olga.kislitsyna@gmail.com
- Tatiana Vladimirovna Chubarova – Doctor of Economics, Professor, Faculty of Management, Shenzhen MSU-BIT University, Shenzhen, 518172, P.R. China; Chief Research Fellow, Institute of Economics of the Russian Academy of Sciences (the RAS). Moscow, 117218, Russia. E-mail: t_chubarova@mail.ru